

NOTES

Titanium-Kaempferol (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy flavone) Complex : A Spectrophotometric Study

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In earlier communications, using spectrophotometric method, physico-chemical constants of uranium, thorium and molybdenum complexes¹ and determination of zirconium² with kaempferol have been reported. The present work concerns the spectrophotometric study of kaempferol-titanium complex.

Kaempferol was synthesised by the method of Robinson et. al.³ and its purity checked by its absorption spectrum in ethanol and thin layer chromatography. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out on a Unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 600 and for *pH* measurements a Metrohm *pH* meter, E-350, was used.

Kaempferol gives yellow-orange coloured complex with titanium which is soluble in aqueous ethanol (50% v/v).

Absorption spectra : A series of solutions containing titanium and the ligand in the ratio 1 : 10 were prepared at different *pH* values. Solutions of kaempferol of same strength were used as blanks under the same conditions. In all the cases, maximum absorption was found to be at 425 *nm*. The nature of the absorption spectra shows the formation of only one complex at all *pH* values. The optical density of solutions of the complex was found to increase with increasing *pH* values. However, subsequent investigations were carried out at *pH* 1.0, since at this *pH* value hydrolysis of titanium is negligible.

Adherence to Beer's Law : The complex obeys Beer's Law in the concentration range 0.0 to 7.5 ppm of titanium. The sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.0088 $\gamma\text{Ti}/\text{cm}^2 \equiv \log I_0/I = 0.001$. The optimum concentration range for accurate determination, as deduced from Ringbom's plot, is 1.585 to 6.3 ppm of titanium.

Composition of the complex. The composition of the complex was determined by using Job's method⁴ of continuous variations and confirmed by slope ratio method⁵ (fig. 1). The metal: ligand ratio in the complex is 1:2. In a similarly constituted ligand i.e. galangin (3,5,7 trihydroxy flavone)⁶, the metal : ligand ratio had also been reported to be 1:2.

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The ligand, though quite sensitive, cannot be recommended for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium since several ions interfere. Some of the ions which have been found to interfere are, Zr^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Th^{4+} , Mo^{6+} , Fe^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , Sc^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Be^{2+} . Rare earths do not interfere at low pH values, but at higher pH values there is serious interference. A prior separation of the accompanying ions is, therefore, essential.

FIG. 1

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